

DualEx: Dual-Space Clustering for Regional Explanations

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Abstract—Regional explanations bridge the gap between local instance-specific and global model-level explanations. However, by relying solely on the model explanation space, existing approaches may suffer from model- and explanation-specific biases. For robust explanations independent of model choices, we propose Dual-Space Regional Explanations (DualEx). DualEx takes an early-fusion, dual-space approach to form regions based on both data space (intrinsic features) and explanation space (feature attributions), weighted through a tunable parameter. We assess faithfulness of regional explanations using established clustering metrics as well as through a novel notion of cohort locality — whether explanations remain consistent and predictive within each region. In a thorough empirical evaluation study, we find that across diverse datasets, models and evaluation metrics, DualEx shows superior region quality than state-of-the-art, and provides interpretable and robust explanations that reflect data structure and model behaviour.

Index Terms—Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI), Explainable Machine Learning (XML), Regional Explanations, Explanations Clustering

I. INTRODUCTION

Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) post-hoc methods mostly target either an individual observation (local explanation) or the model in its entirety (global explanation) [1]. Where local explanations capture the model’s behaviour at a single point, global explanations summarise the model’s behaviour more generally. While they offer relevant insights, they may be too specific or general to describe which types of inputs lead to which types of outputs at an intermediate level. Regional explanations has therefore emerged as a new type of explanation to bridge this gap. They identify coherent groups within the data with respect to a particular machine learning model, and provide explanations specific to each of these groups. Such regional explanations are beneficial in many applications, especially in high-risk domains such as healthcare. Consider a machine learning model for a particular disease. If the goal is to understand why the machine learning model makes a particular prediction, local explanations are

suited: for example, in Fig. 1 patient A on the top left is described by a local explanation in the form of feature importance, signalling how much each of the five features contributes to the prediction.

Across all patients, global explanations offer an overview over model behaviour. In the example, the global explanation indicates the extent to which the model overall relies on different features in making its prediction.

Regional explanations enable us to understand the extent to which the local explanation generalises to similar observations (patients) and the extent to which the overall model behaviour is consistent across observations (patients). In our example in Fig. 1, to understand whether patient A’s symptoms are typical or more rare, with local (top left) and global explanations (bottom left) only, we can compare their feature importance directly, but might be unaware of whether other patients are similar to A, and different from the global average.

For a more profound analysis of how patient A compares, regional explanations (in Fig. 1 right) should offer a succinct summary over observations that are similar, and are treated similarly by the model. Regional explanations should thus be faithful representations of these two aspects.

However, current regional explanations suffer from what we here term *model bias*, because they determine regions based on the *explanation space*: we here differentiate between *data space* with the actual feature values for the observations (a patient when studying medical data) such as temperature, blood pressure, biochemical measurements, etc., and *explanation space* with the importance attribution of each feature w.r.t. some predictive model (such as a neural network trained to support diagnosis), and with respect to some feature attribution model (e.g. LIME [2] or SHAP [3] which quantify the impact of each feature on the decision of the predictive model).

We claim that model bias is an overlooked issue that greatly harms robustness of regional explanations in existing work: if patient groups can change seemingly unpredictably depending

Fig. 1: Local explanation: feature importance for patient A’s prediction (top left); Global explanation: average importance across all patients (bottom left); Regional explanation: average importance for groups with similar behaviour, supporting easy comparison within (patient A in Region 1) and between regions (importance of A’s Region 1 vs. other regions) (right).

on the choice of feature attribution method, trustworthiness and reliability of explanations are undermined. On the other hand, simply grouping in data space may not determine coherent regions that can be effectively summarised by consistent explanations.

Our approach thus combines both views: the data space, with actual feature values for similarity of observations (patients), and the explanation space, with feature attribution to reflect the importance of the model in making predictions (characteristic symptoms). This ensures that regions summarise patients who are both similar in their attributes and treated similarly by the model. As shown in Fig. 1, regions are characterised by their explanations (feature importance bars) and their feature values (ranges in feature space where patients are closely together).

Our contributions are the following:

- We formalise Dual-Space Regional Explanations and distinguish our approach from purely explanation-space-driven regional explanations.
- We introduce a multi-view clustering methodology that uses a combined distance metric, which reduces model-induced biases by utilising the data and explanation space.
- Through extensive empirical validation on diverse datasets, various machine learning models, and validation metrics, we demonstrate that our method achieves more robust, interpretable, and meaningful regional explanations overall, and in comparison to existing methods.

The remainder of this paper will proceed with related work in Section II encompassing of an overview of current post-hoc feature attribution methods, regional explanation approaches, and multi-view clustering. Then, Section III will sequentially detail our dual-space method, followed by Section IV showing in-depth experiments of our method. Finally, we conclude in

Section V and look towards future work.

II. RELATED WORK

To contextualise our novel approach to regional explanations, we focus on three areas in the related work: post-hoc feature attribution methods, existing regional explanation approaches, and multi-view clustering, emphasising work that involves weighting distances across different spaces.

A. Scope of Explanations

Various methods for XAI exist [4]–[7], many are designed for deep learning [8]–[11] and others are model-agnostic [2], [3], [12], [13]. We focus on the scope of explanations, emphasising the two arguably most prominent methods, which are the ones used in the regional explanations literature: LIME [2] and SHAP [3].

LIME provides local and global explanations creating a synthetic dataset and fitting an interpretable surrogate model to determine feature importance. However, the data generation process creates instability in the scores [14], [15], resulting in different local explanations for the same observation.

SHAP is a unified approach to explaining the output of any machine learning model by using the concept of Shapley values from game theory [16]. The method provides both local and global explanations. Local explanations are the impact of each observation having a particular feature value compared to the prediction without that feature value, with the estimation carried out by evaluating all feature coalitions. Global explanations are averages of local ones.

In context of regional explanations, LIME and approaches estimating Shapley values, with SHAP being the most popular, are the feature importance attribution methods that have been studied. XAI methods trying to approximate Shapley values have been shown [17] to perform better than LIME.

B. Regional Explanations

In the literature, there are several studies exploring groupings of explanations. Most works group feature importance attributions while some aggregate other local explanation methods such as Individual Conditional Expectations [18]–[20]. In our work, we focus on grouping local feature importance attributions.

Early literature on regional explanations by Lundberg et al. [3], [21], only clusters the explanation space, and discusses supervised learning approaches to aggregating explanations. They focus on hierarchical clustering of SHAP vectors to identify groups of observations with similar explanations.

The effectiveness of regional explanations in real-world tasks is underscored by several papers focusing on specific applications [22]–[27]. Contexts investigated range from high-impact medical datasets [22], [23] to insurance coverage data [24]. Regardless of the specific application scenario, authors select a single machine learning model to fit the explanation space, and then retrieve regional explanations leveraging standard clustering algorithms such as k -means. Aggregation of data subgroups allows us to find regions coherent with domain experts’ indication [22].

Exemplified in Schulz et al. [27], they highlight the advantages of clustering in the explanation space, noting that the embeddings collapse irrelevant features and produce more compact clusters through emphasising prediction-relevant aspects. While this demonstrates the interpretive power of explanation-based groups, clusters derived solely from explanations remain tightly coupled to the specific predictive model. As we later show in Section IV, explanation-only clustering can vary substantially across models, undermining robustness. DualEx complements the benefits identified by Schulz et al. through retaining the compactness of the explanation space while simultaneously anchoring clusters in the data space, thereby mitigating model-induced bias and improving stability across predictive models.

Although such works have explored clustering feature importance attribution to allow a deeper data analysis in specific examples, they do not evaluate the contribution of explanation clustering as a whole [17]. Moreover, the effect of the machine learning model on the analysis is not studied, overlooking model-induced bias.

A more comprehensive study on regional explanations is presented by Escrivá et al. [17]. The authors use a Random Forest model to fit an extensive collection of real-world datasets. Different clustering algorithms are then employed to cluster the feature importance attributions. Comparison between clustering the explanation space and clustering the data space shows that the former allows for better separation between instances, resulting in higher quality clusters [17]. Better performance in the explanation space is mainly attributed to importance scores conveying less noise than the original features and preserving the most significant information only. Thereby, the explanation space is by nature more compact and separable. Moreover, analysing different

XAI feature importance methods leads to the conclusion that SHAP values are more suitable for regional explanations than competitors e.g., LIME. Escrivá et al. [17] recognise that the ML model might influence the regions but limit their analysis to showing that good regions are retrieved also when low-accuracy models are employed, without evaluating the difference in the regions produced by different models. Furthermore, the data space and the explanation space are clustered separately and the information coming from the two spaces is not jointly exploited.

Meng et al. [28] study regional explanations under Cohort Explanations (CohEx). Their work assumes clustering algorithms where the expected number of regions is given as an input parameter. At each iteration step, multiple importance values need to be recomputed, leading to a high computational demand. Similarity is solely measured in the data space, while convergence is checked by evaluating in the explanation space. Thus, information from the explanation space is not considered when computing similarities between instances. Moreover, the proposed cohort explanations show higher variance than competitors, lacking stability [28]. Meng et al. [28] strive for consistency in their explanations but only target inconsistency deriving from the feature importance methods, e.g., SHAP’s approximation strategy, without addressing bias induced by the machine learning model. We study the impact of these model choices and CohEx performance in our empirical evaluation.

C. Multi-View Clustering

Multi-view clustering can be seen as a special case of ensemble clustering and aims at finding the best data partition when multiple data representations (views), exist for each object [29]. Advances in information acquisition have prompted multi-view clustering to gain relevance [30] as data are often described by multiple views. Applications span several fields ranging from molecules that can be represented by their amino acid structure and by their 3D representation [31], images with different feature representations [32], to news being reported by multiple news organizations [31], [33].

The effectiveness of multi-view clustering is based on the compatibility and complementary principles [30], [33], [34]. Compatibility refers to the common knowledge shared by the different views [30], granting a clustering outcome which is meaningful in each view. The complementary principle instead affirms that each view contains unique knowledge [33] allowing for a better clustering outcome.

Early works on multi-view clustering propose extensions to popular clustering algorithms when multiple views are available. Specifically, Bickel et al. [35] study multi-view versions of agglomerative, hierarchical and expectation maximization based clustering. Kailing et al. [31] focus instead on density-based clustering tackling DBSCAN.

More generally, according to the taxonomy introduced in [30], multi-view approaches can be divided into three categories: direct fusion, early fusion, and late fusion. The type of fusion depends on when the information from multiple views is merged. In direct fusion algorithms, specific loss

functions incorporating each data representation are optimized. Late fusion approaches cluster each view separately before merging the clustering outcomes into the final data partition. Our approach leverages instead an early fusion strategy, i.e., information from multiple views is exploited to build a consensus affinity structure, used to apply well-known clustering algorithms such as k -means.

Another instance of an early fusion strategy is the work by Chen et al. [36]. The authors, similarly to our work, propose a combined distance matrix which takes into account pairwise similarities from each view. Contrary to our proposal, their framework weights each view equally, and the similarity matrix is exploited to perform spectral clustering.

III. DUAL-SPACE EVALUATION CONCEPT

Our dual-space evaluation concept systematically integrates insights from the data and explanation space. Our approach addresses the inherent problems that arise when clustering is conducted exclusively in either the data space or the explanation space by explicitly balancing the two spaces.

When clustering solely in the data or explanation space, specific trade-offs occur. Firstly, clustering purely in the data space provides groupings based on intrinsic model-independent features, capturing the inherent structural patterns present in the data. However, it disregards the model-specific insights which can improve meaningful subgroup identification because it reduces noise through recognising only relevant features. Conversely, clustering solely within the explanation space captures how predictive models reason about specific predictions but embeds biases. Biases are inherent to the model training and explanation generation processes. Different models capture different correlation patterns. Dependent on the model architecture and parameters, each embeds different biases and produce different model explanations.

Our approach integrates these complementary spaces to avoid one extreme or the other. By combining both spaces, we get the ‘best of both worlds’, and our method enhances the stability, robustness, and general applicability of regional explanations.

Cluster stability is one major strength of our dual-space approach. Clusters will be more stable because they are less sensitive to fluctuations from the model behaviour or from slight variations in the data. As both spaces influence the clusters, they are less likely to shift dramatically if the model or data changes. Hence, this will improve the reproducibility and reliability of the clustering outcomes without sacrificing clustering performance, which become apparent later in our experiments in Section IV.

Another core strength is the enhancement of generalisability as clusterings solely based on the explanation space may overfit specific model abnormalities. By incorporating the intrinsic structure of the data, dual-space clustering becomes more robust across different models and datasets. Henceforth, this makes the resulting clusterings broadly applicable, supporting analyses that extend beyond a single model instance.

The remainder of this section details the practical implementation of our dual-space evaluation concept. First we formally define the data and explanation space and the combined distance metric together with the role of a tuning parameter, which we denote as α . We then discuss how we obtain clustering outcomes and map clusters to regional explanations. Lastly, we evaluate to gain insights into the regional explanations.

A. Data and Explanation Space

A dataset \mathcal{D} consists of $|\mathcal{D}| = n$ observations. We denote the i -th observation’s data vector in the data space as \mathbf{x}_i with m features as: $\mathbf{x}_i = (\mathbf{x}_{i_1}, \mathbf{x}_{i_2}, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{i_m})$. Similarly, given a feature attribution method and a classifier to explain, we define an observation i ’s explanation vector ϕ_i in the explanation space as: $\phi_i = (\phi_{i_1}, \phi_{i_2}, \dots, \phi_{i_m})$, where ϕ_{i_j} indicates the importance of feature j for classifying observation i according to the attribution method and classifier.

We begin by distinguishing two complementary spaces of each observation i : its data vector \mathbf{x}_i , containing the original feature values, and its explanation vector ϕ_i , containing the feature-attribution scores produced by the trained predictive model. To obtain clusterings that are simultaneously faithful to the intrinsic data patterns and to the model’s reasoning, we introduce a tuning parameter $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ that interpolates between the two spaces:

- $\alpha = 0 \rightarrow$ ignore explanations; distances are computed solely in the data space.
- $\alpha = 1 \rightarrow$ ignore raw attributes; distances are computed solely in the explanation space.
- $0 < \alpha < 1 \rightarrow$ distances are obtained from a *weighted combination* of the two spaces in the ratio $\alpha : (1 - \alpha)$.

Varying α lets us move from a purely data-driven partitioning to a purely explanation-driven one, with intermediate values providing a trade-off: distances reflect the data space with weight α and the explanation space with weight $(1 - \alpha)$. In practice, the trade-off is implemented through a combined-distance metric defined in (1); first, we describe the intuition complemented with a visual example, before delving into the formal definition.

Fig. 2 shows the effect of the trade-off visually. In our example, we utilise the binarised Semeion dataset of the original Semeion handwritten digit dataset from openML [37] and obtain a 2D representation through Multi-Dimensional Scaling (MDS) [38], [39], a data mining technique visualising the similarity between observations given a number of dimensions. Prior to performing MDS, we construct the explanation space by training a Random Forest classifier on the binary task and then compute the explanation space given the model. With the data and explanation space, we compute distances between the observations using our combined distance metric; we choose $\alpha = 0, 0.5$, and 1. Based on the best clustering outcomes at each α -evaluated through an internal validation metric we leverage MDS and build a 2D space for each.

The left view shows clusters obtained when $\alpha = 0$, plotted in the original feature space (X_1, X_2) . The data space clustering outcome projection shows some structure with one

Fig. 2: The three views show the 2D projections through Multi-Dimensional Scaling (MDS) of the dataset Semeion with $\alpha = 0, 0.5$ and 1 , showing the transition from pure data space to pure explanation space. Below the projected spaces are the corresponding regional explanations.

compact region. Overall, observations within the data space are not grouped in well-separated regions. For the data space, our internal validation metric score is 0.64.

The far-right view shows the same observations in the explanation space (ϕ_1, ϕ_2) that results from $\alpha = 1$, where clusters are dictated entirely by the model’s reasoning. The projection testifies how the explanation space allows the identification of compact and separated regions, although at the cost of model bias-infused regions. For the explanation space, our internal validation metric score is 0.75.

The middle view depicts an intermediate setting, which can be any value within $0 < \alpha < 1$; for exemplification, we choose $\alpha = 0.5$, which is the exact middle between the extreme of the data and explanation space and thus, is the point of which the trade-off is equal, balancing the information from both spaces. The regions are more compact and cohesive than the data space but less than the explanation space, and we obtain an internal validation metric score of 0.69.

The hybrid view at $\alpha = 0.5$ inherits the data space’s broad structure while gaining the explanation space’s compactness—capturing the ‘best of both worlds’ as later experiments will confirm, cluster stability and generalisability peak at intermediate α values, echoing the qualitative impression conveyed by the figure. Accompanying each view, we provide regional explanations that highlight how the features differ for each region. For simplicity, we have chosen to present only three features for each region.

In the far-left view, which illustrates data space clustering, the top three features are pink, green, and orange for both regions, although they vary in magnitude. In contrast, the explanation space reveals two regions with a different set

of top three features, excluding pink but including green, orange, grey, and brown. Between these two perspectives, the dual-space outcome presents similar feature attributions for the regions in both the data and explanation spaces. This demonstrates how the dual-space outcomes utilise both spaces to achieve a balanced result.

B. Combined Distance Metric

Multi-view clustering includes analysis of data from multiple views (perspectives) simultaneously [40]–[42], to find meaningful patterns that would not be found from a single view alone. By leveraging different representations of the same data (different views), we can combine them rather than treat them independently, leading to more robust and accurate clustering results. In our setting, the two views are the data and the explanation space, and our goal is to obtain a consensus clustering that balances information from both. To achieve this, we propose a combined distance metric that incorporates distances from the two spaces, with their relative influence controlled through a tunable parameter α .

Consider a dataset consisting of instances $\{x_i\}_{i=1}^n$, each instance $x_i \in \mathbb{R}^m$ with m features. A predictive model $f(\cdot)$ trained on this data produces predictions and corresponding explanations, where each instance x_i has an associated explanation vector $\phi_i \in \mathbb{R}^m$, representing feature attributions.

We define the combined distance metric between two objects x_i and x_j as:

$$d_{\text{comb}}(i, j) = \sqrt{(1 - \alpha) \cdot [d_{\text{data}}(i, j)]^2 + \alpha \cdot [d_{\text{expl}}(i, j)]^2} \quad (1)$$

where $d_{\text{comb}}(i, j)$ represents the combined distance between points i and j , $d_{\text{data}}(i, j)$ is the distance in the data space,

and $d_{\text{expl}}(i, j)$ is the distance in the explanation space. Each instance x_i is associated with an explanation vector $\phi \in \mathbb{R}^m$, obtained from any feature attribution method (e.g., SHAP, LIME). The explanation space distance is then defined as the Euclidean distance between explanation vectors: $d_{\text{expl}}(i, j) = \|\phi_i - \phi_j\|_2$, capturing differences in the feature attributions assigned to the two instances. Moreover, to ensure comparability such that α reflects the weight between the two spaces, we normalise both d_{data} and d_{expl} prior to computing the combined distance matrix, securing that their average magnitudes are on the same scale and guaranteeing that $\alpha = 0.5$ represents an equal contribution from the data- and explanation space.

In practice, choosing α is domain-dependent. A high α emphasises prediction-relevant structure and can mitigate spurious variation in raw features, whereas a low α anchors clusters firmly in the input space, preferable when explanation methods are noisy or unstable. Thus, we view α as a user-controllable weight rather than a fixed constant. Our sensitivity analysis in Table III and Figure 4 show that increasing α tends to improve internal validity while reducing cross-model stability, highlighting a robustness–validity trade-off. Accordingly, in the experiments we set $\alpha = 0.5$ as a neutral default: after normalising distances in each space, $\alpha = 0.5$ yields equal contributions from data and explanation, avoids dataset-specific tuning, and isolates the effect of dual-space fusion. We use the sensitivity analysis to contextualise deviations from this default when necessary. While the optimal α can be task-specific, our results indicate that intermediate values (including $\alpha \approx 0.5$) often lie near favourable points on the validity–stability frontier, making it a practical baseline choice.

C. Forming Regional Explanations

For a chosen weight $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ we collect all pair-wise distances into an $n \times n$ matrix:

$$\mathbf{D}^{(\alpha)} \quad \text{where} \quad D_{ij}^{(\alpha)} = d_{\text{comb}}(i, j) \quad (\text{Eq. 1}).$$

Once the pair-wise distances are weighted by α (Eq. 1), the next step is to obtain concrete sub-populations. The similarity relationships computed with our combined distance metric, are input to hard clustering algorithms, e.g., k -means, Agglomerative Clustering, DBSCAN, HDBSCAN, etc. The algorithms employed return a grouping of observations (n) in the dataset. Then, the clustering outcome is mapped to the explanation space: each cluster index set becomes a region of explanations. The regional explanations are retrieved as the average of the feature importance attributions for each cluster.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}^{(\alpha)} &= \{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_k\}, \\ \bigcup_{\ell=1}^k C_\ell &= \{1, \dots, n\}, \quad C_\ell \cap C_{\ell'} = \emptyset. \end{aligned}$$

Each index set C_ℓ naturally corresponds to a meaningful partition of the data space reflecting dual-space similarity, as the underlying distances combine raw attributes and explanation vectors. If the chosen clustering algorithm labels points as noise, each noise point becomes a singleton region, and

retains its original local explanation. During the evaluation, we follow the penalty strategy of [43]: singletons do not contribute to compactness scores but proportionally lower the overall internal validation metric if they become too numerous; preventing artificial inflation of validity metrics.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

Datasets & reproducibility. We evaluate our regional explanation method across a number of classification datasets from OpenML [37] A comprehensive list detailing task IDs, dataset statistics, and reproducible code is available at the following GitHub repository ¹. **Predictive models.** For thorough evaluation across classifier models, we study Random Forest (RF) [44], Gradient Boosting (GB), XGBoost [45], Decision Tree (DT) [46], and feed-forward neural network (MLP). Hyper-parameters are optimised using 5-fold stratified grid search using $F1$ -Score to select the best-performing models per dataset. **Local explanations.** Local explanations for predictions use SHAP (ϕ_i); specifically, TreeExplainer [47] for tree-based models and KernelExplainer [3] for MLPClassifier. Before constructing the combined distance matrix, attributions are standardised (feature-wise z-normalization [48]) to ensure comparability across features. **Clustering.** We study different clustering paradigms: Hierarchical Agglomerative Clustering [49], Density-based DBSCAN [50], Hierarchical density-based HDBSCAN [51], and partitioning-based k -medoids [52]. Default value for $\alpha = 0.5$ unless states otherwise. **Evaluation Metrics.** We use **Silhouette Coefficient (SC)** [53] to assess compactness and separation of clusters, suitable primarily for convex-shaped clusters as in partitioning-based clustering methods. **Density-Based Clustering Validation (DBC)** [43] captures arbitrary cluster shapes effectively, suitable for density-based clustering. **Adjusted Rand Index (ARI)** — Quantifies similarity between predicted clusters and ground-truth class labels; serves as an external, supervised measure of clustering where ground truth is available. **Normalized Mutual Information (NMI)** [54]: Measures the similarity between two clusterings—in our study, we use it compare across different predictive models—providing an indicator of clustering robustness and cross-model consistency.

A. Comparative Evaluation

We first benchmark our Dual-Space Explanations (DualEx) method against the state-of-the-art regional explanation method CohEx [28]. Both CohEx and our DualEx utilise information from model explanations, but they differ fundamentally: CohEx performs centroid-based clustering in the data space and only evaluates clusters in the explanation space post-hoc, whereas DualEx exploits both data- and explanation-space information to form regions.

For comparability to CohEx, we restrict DualEx to k -medoids clustering in this experiment, but please note that our DualEx is more general and supports other clustering models as well. Moreover, in this first experiment, in DualEx we

¹<https://github.com/PernilleMathews/DualEx>

TABLE I: Cluster validity (Silhouette Coefficient \uparrow) for DualEx vs. CohEx. Better method marked in bold.

Dataset	DualEx	CohEx
ionosphere	0.28	0.25
bodyfat	0.34	0.24
ar4	0.55	0.28
heart-c	0.17	0.20
challenger	0.67	0.35

TABLE II: Cross-model robustness (NMI \uparrow) for DualEx vs. CohEx. Better method marked in bold.

Dataset	DualEx	CohEx
ionosphere	0.59	0.27
bodyfat	0.44	0.38
ar4	0.73	0.54
heart-c	0.56	0.34
challenger	0.81	0.63

fix $\alpha = 0.5$; equally weighting data- and explanation-space distances. This setting is a baseline trade-off where neither space dominates for studying whether dual-space integration itself is beneficial. Alternative weighting settings are studied in later experiments.

We test $k \in 2, 3, 4, 5$ for both methods. The value of k that maximises the SC on each (dataset, method) pair is retained for evaluation. Due to the high computational complexity of CohEx, we test on five smaller datasets: *bodyfat*, *ionosphere*, *ar4*, *heart-c*, and *challenger* [37], and use 3 machine learning models: MLP, RF and GB. Note we evaluate DualEx with $\alpha = 0.5$, while CohEx is evaluated in its explanation space, as defined in their method.

Table I reports SCs. In four of five datasets, DualEx achieves higher SC than CohEx, indicating regions that are simultaneously more compact and better separated. The most significant gains occur in *ar4* and *challenger*, while *heart-c* shows a slight decrease in SC for DualEx. This drop may be explained by the dataset’s higher dimensionality and noise, where the explanatory space provides less benefit to the cluster structure. Nevertheless, even on *heart-c*, the difference is marginal.

Table II evaluates robustness using average pairwise Normalised Mutual Information (NMI). Unlike its use for ground-truth comparison, here NMI measures agreement between clusterings induced by different models. DualEx achieves consistently higher NMI than CohEx, demonstrating that its regions are more stable across models. This stability is an important feature of DualEx, as different explanations for the same data are likely experienced as confusing by users. Our stability in DualEx stems from integrating explanation space information, while preserving original structure from the data space. In contrast, CohEx’s post-hoc evaluation leads to centroids that vary more erratically across models, leading to substantially less robust results.

B. Sensitivity Analysis

When utilising machine learning models, one often deploys several predictive models in parallel or updates a model over time; with DualEx, we show through this second experiment that our method across models allows stable clustering outcomes, i.e., outcomes that remain similar regardless of the model or hyper-parameters. To observe the average on a global level, we utilise 60 randomly selected binary classification datasets from OpenML, DBSCAN and k -medoids for clustering and SC, DBCV, ARI for validation.

The objective is to quantify the extent of model-induced bias in the clustering outcomes, or equivalently, how robust the partitions are across different predictive models. We do this by computing the pairwise NMI across outcomes across the set of machine learning models employed. Specifically, we train 5 architectures for each dataset: a MLP, a RF, DT, GB and XGBoost.

To obtain model feature attributions we employ SHAP. Due to the foundation of methods like SHAP, the five model architectures produce different explanation spaces; biasing the clustering outcome. We perform a cross-validated grid search to choose the best hyper-parameters for each model.

To achieve the average pairwise NMI, we first average the ten pairwise comparisons between the five predictive models for each dataset, then average between datasets.

First we report and visualise the average DBCV score and pairwise NMI for DBSCAN. We see in Fig. 3 the outcomes from DualEx at $\alpha = 0$ (data space), 0.5 (dual-space) and 1 (explanation space). Moreover, in the figure, the shaded area behind the two metric lines shows the lowest and highest NMI observed at each α across datasets. These values expose the spread of the best and worst-case stability across datasets.

In Fig. 3, we observe how the NMI starts at a perfect NMI at $\alpha = 0$, where all clustering outcomes are equal, and no model bias exists; only the data space is being clustered. For $\alpha = 0.5$ the NMI drops, while the internal validation score (DBCV) remains the same, the drop is caused by the explanation space distances now take part in the combined distance matrix. The model bias from the explanations now play a role within the combined distance metric and, thereby, for the clustering outcomes.

Lastly, for $\alpha = 1$, we see an increase in the internal validation score. The higher DBCV score is due to the explanation space being much more compact and cohesive than the remaining spaces due to the feature attribution values. Recall from Fig. 2 where we saw that as α increases, the spaces become much more compact and separable as model bias influences the outcomes more and more. For the average NMI at $\alpha = 1$, we observe how the NMI drops, expectedly, due to the feature attributions in the explanation space differing due to model bias across models, making the outcomes more distinct across models at higher α ’s. We re-iterate the trade-off that can be seen in this global trend; as in the previous experiment, one can obtain a higher internal validation score at the cost of robustness between models and model variation.

Beyond observing the trend for the average NMI for the different α values in Fig. 3, we explore a more comprehensive analysis through observing the trend from $\alpha = 0, 0.1 \dots 1$, across multiple clustering algorithms, and internal validation metrics. Table III shows the comprehensive results for three validation metrics: SC, DBCV and ARI.

By colour encoding each cell, it becomes easy to visually inspect the results. For the mean NMI column, the green colouring shows the maximum agreement between models (maximum robustness and minimum bias); darker red colour indicates less agreement between models.

Fig. 3: Given 60 datasets, we observe the data, dual-space and explanation space. The figure details how the average pairwise NMI and DBCV for the DBSCAN clustering algorithm changes as more model-bias is infused into the model meanwhile the NMI Min-Max values expose the spread of the best and worst-case stability across datasets.

Moreover, in all tables, we show the minimum and maximum values, exposing the spread of the best and worst-case stability across datasets. For minimum values, if the value is very low (red), the stability is poor, while if higher (orange or green), the stability is intermediate or high. In the maximum column, a high maximum average means we can obtain high NMI outcomes at the given α (on average).

For each table and its α -values, we see the rows side-by-side, which reveal our method’s typical and extreme behaviour as it shifts from data-driven outcomes ($\alpha = 0$) to model-only outcomes ($\alpha = 1$). For all metrics, the monotonic transition from green to red corroborates that model-specific bias increases—and cross-model consensus decreases when the explanation space dominates.

Table III shows how smaller values of α combine information from the data and the explanation space, making the outcome less biased. Moreover, as testified by the *Max* column, clustering assignments can be maximally robust (NMI = 1) at high values of α . This implies that, while we obtain valuable information from the data space, making regions more separated, we leverage the data space information to ensure more stable clustering.

C. Case Study: 2D Regression Task

We now study a case using the RABE_266 dataset from OpenML, originally from “Regression Analysis” by John Wiley [55]. The dataset contains 120 observations for a regression task predicting a real-valued response y from two continuous predictors ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 , evenly spaced over $\phi_1 \in [-60, 50]$ and $\phi_2 \in [5, 50]$, yielding a balanced, low-dimensional data space. This setting is well-suited for illustrating how regional explanations change with α when different predictive models induce different explanation spaces. Because the task involves only two predictors and 120 observations, the global relationship between ϕ_1 , ϕ_2 and y is close to linear, which provides a clean baseline to highlight how more complex models introduce variation in the explanation space.

TABLE III: Robustness: per metric (SC, DBCV and ARI) and α : mean is dataset-averaged pairwise NMI between five models; min/max NMI per dataset at each α . Colour scale from green (robust) to red (unstable).

α	SC			DBCV			ARI		
	mean	min	max	mean	min	max	mean	min	max
0.0	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
0.1	.78	.25	1.00	.75	.25	1.00	.66	.21	1.00
0.2	0.71	0.18	1.00	0.68	0.15	1.00	0.60	0.25	1.00
0.3	0.64	0.20	1.00	0.61	0.18	1.00	0.54	0.15	0.96
0.4	0.58	0.05	0.85	0.54	0.06	0.86	0.51	0.06	0.83
0.5	0.49	0.11	0.84	0.48	0.11	0.84	0.43	0.11	0.73
0.6	0.47	0.11	0.80	0.44	0.17	0.81	0.42	0.14	0.72
0.7	0.43	0.02	0.75	0.41	0.02	0.78	0.40	0.04	0.76
0.8	0.39	0.03	0.75	0.38	0.03	0.73	0.38	0.05	0.75
0.9	0.36	0.02	0.74	0.35	0.01	0.66	0.37	0.08	0.74
1.0	0.36	0.03	0.74	0.34	0.08	0.74	0.36	0.07	0.79

We employ three models: a MLP, a RF, and GB. We cluster their outcomes using k -medoids, selecting the optimal number of clusters k via grid search on the SC. Regional explanations obtained by clustering the combined data and explanation space reveal where each model focuses its attention within that global trend. They answer questions such as “Does the model rely more on ϕ_1 or ϕ_2 in this part of the space?” and “Are different models focusing on the same sub-structures?”.

In Fig. 4, we visualise cluster validity (SC) and cross-model robustness (NMI) as α increases. The SC shows that incorporating explanation-space information improves intra-cluster compactness and inter-cluster separation. At the same time, the NMI trend highlights the trade-off that model-specific feature attributions introduce bias, lowering agreement across models. Thus, while higher α enhances regional coherence, it simultaneously reduces robustness across classifiers.

Simultaneously, Fig. 4 shows how cross-model NMI decreases as α increases. While NMI is 1 in the data space (independent of the model), more emphasis on the explanation space introduces model-specific bias; reducing agreement across clustering outcomes. Thus, regional explanations increasingly reflect model bias rather than the underlying data.

Fig. 6a and 6b showcase the regional feature importances for $\alpha = 0.5$. The explanations are relatively homogeneous between the two regions, with ϕ_2 in region 2 having lower importance than in region 1. By comparing the results across the data space in Fig. 5, dual-space in Fig. 6, and explanation space in Fig. 7, from the visualisations it is clear how DualEx significantly enhances regional coherence. The dual-space clusters display a more apparent separation of predictions, as visible in the parallel coordinate plots, and yield more consistent and distinct feature attributions within each region.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a novel dual-space approach for regional explanations that combines distances in the data and explanation spaces via a tunable parameter α . By integrating both view, our method balances data-driven cohesion with

Fig. 4: Internal validity (SC) and cross-model agreement (NMI) vs. $\alpha[0 : 1]$ for RABE266 dataset. SC increases, the explanation space improves cohesion and separation but NMI decreases as model-specific bias reduces agreement.

Fig. 5: Data Space Regions 1 & 2 for dataset RABE 266. Top plots show the feature importances based on the data space. Bottom plots show the feature values per region.

model-driven interpretability, addressing limitations of existing methods that either ignore the data space or suffer from model bias in the explanation space.

In our experiments, we conduct a large-scale stability study across 60 OpenML classification datasets, five machine learning models, and three validation metrics. Our results reveal that cross-model robustness tends to be achieved for approximately even balance between data and explanation spaces.

Practically adopting regional explanations should be supported by interactive tools to allow practitioners to vary α on the fly, inspect regional explanations, and compare outcomes across machine learning models. Lastly, comparisons with other attribution methods such as LIME, Integrated Gradients, or permutation importance are interesting future work.

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Fig. 6: Dual-Space Regions 1 & 2 for dataset RABE 266. Top plots show feature importance and bottom plots display regional separation, showing how DualEx leverages explanatory information to enhance clustering coherence.

Fig. 7: Explanation Space Regions 1, 2, & 3 for dataset RABE 266. Top feature importances in the expl. space; bottom separation when relying solely on the model’s explanations.

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